

Multimodal Stress Classification Using Physiological Signals and Facial Expressions with Machine and Deep Learning Models

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Abstract—Stress detection has become increasingly important in modern healthcare and wellness applications. This paper presents a comparative study of machine and deep learning approaches for stress classification using physiological signals and facial expressions. Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) models are evaluated for analyzing physiological data including electrodermal activity, blood volume pressure, skin temperature, and accelerometer readings across 15, 30, and 60-second time windows. VGG16 and a Custom Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) are deployed for stress classification from 48x48 grayscale facial images data. Using the WorkStress3D dataset, experimental results demonstrate that LSTM achieves test accuracies of 80%, 85%, and 86% for the data with 15, 30, and 60-second time windows respectively, outperforming SVM. For facial expressions, VGG16 attains 87% test accuracy, surpassing the custom CNN’s 81%. The findings reveal that longer time windows enhance physiological signal-based predictions, while both CNN architectures effectively capture stress-indicative facial features, establishing a foundation for robust stress monitoring systems.

Index Terms—Stress detection, physiological signals, facial expressions, LSTM, SVM, CNN, VGG16, deep learning, WorkStress3D dataset

I. INTRODUCTION

Stress is a prevalent and consequential aspect of modern life, impacting individuals both mentally and physically. Stress affects mood, behavior, and health. Short-term stress can be adaptive, but long-term exposure can lead to health issues [1]. Recognizing and understanding stress is crucial for maintaining well-being, and technological advancements have enabled the exploration of innovative approaches to stress detection. This work delves into the domain of stress analysis, focusing on two distinct data modalities: physiological signals and facial expressions.

A. Problem Statement

The challenge addressed in this study is the accurate classification of stress levels using physiological signals and facial expressions. Stress assessment traditionally relies on self-reporting, which can be subjective and prone to biases. Leveraging advanced technologies, such as machine learning models, offers the potential for objective and real-time stress detection. However, developing robust models for stress classification requires overcoming challenges related to diverse data sources, varying time windows, and the intricate nature of stress manifestations.

B. Motivation

The motivation behind this work stems from the potential societal impact of reliable stress detection. By harnessing physiological signals, including electrodermal activity, blood volume pressure, skin temperature, and accelerometer data, alongside facial expressions, we aim to create models that can provide objective insights into an individual’s stress state. The outcomes of this research can contribute to the development of proactive stress management strategies, leading to improved mental health and overall well-being.

The choice of employing Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) models for physiological signals, as well as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) such as VGG16 and a Custom CNN for facial expressions, is grounded in their effectiveness in capturing temporal dependencies and image features. The exploration of diverse models allows us to comprehensively assess their performance in stress classification across different data types and time windows.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent studies, researchers have focused on assessing the emotional response of individuals in various contexts to better understand stress and its implications [2], [3]. For instance, [2] investigates how different car handling setups affect drivers’ stress levels, using physiological signals like skin potential responses (SPRs) and electrocardiogram (ECG) signals. Similarly, [3] explores stress alleviation methods using virtual reality (VR) video games, analyzing physiological signals such as ECG, galvanic skin response (GSR), and respiration (RESP) to determine stress levels.

Moreover, there’s a growing recognition of the importance of monitoring stress levels among specific demographics, such as college students, due to escalating stress levels in academic and familial settings [4]. This study utilizes physiological signals like photoplethysmography (PPG), ECG, and EEG to assess stress levels among students engaged in Sudoku games under different conditions.

Furthermore, traditional methods of detecting mental stress, such as interviews and questionnaires, may not capture instantaneous emotional responses effectively [5]. Instead, approaches like experience sampling and multi-modal fusion models have shown promise in accurately identifying and

classifying stress levels based on physiological signals, facial expressions, and auditory data.

Overall, these studies highlight the significance of understanding stress dynamics and the potential of advanced technologies and methodologies in stress detection and management. Furthermore, our approach draws inspiration from recent studies in stress detection, such as those utilizing multi-modal fusion techniques, where researchers combined different types of data to understand stress levels better. Similarly, we've created a fusion model by combining outputs (probabilities or features) from LSTM and VGG16 models to classify stress. While our work shares the idea of combining data sources for better accuracy, we've tailored our method to suit our specific task, focusing solely on the outputs of these models. This shows how fusion models can be adapted to various research goals and areas.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed for this work includes dataset preparation, model implementation and model evaluation. This work attempts to implement LSTM and SVM model for physiological signals data and CNN models such as VGG16 and our Custom CNN for facial expressions data. The complete source code and implementation details are available at this repository¹.

A. Data Description

Stress analysis from physiological data under pressure: WorkStress3D Dataset [6] is mainly used for this work. For the scope of this study we use only physiological signals data and facial expression data from the WorkStress3D dataset for classifying stress. The physiological signal component file incorporates electrodermal activity (EDA), blood volume pressure (BVP), skin temperature, and accelerometer (ACC) data with the corresponding emotion class (0: stress-free, 1: stressful). There are a total of 3 csv files with these data collected over 15, 30, and 60 seconds data window. Similarly, facial expression data consist of pixels from 48 x 48 grayscale images which are categorized as either stress-free (class 0) or stressful (class 1). Figure. 1 shows the data distribution of the dataset.

B. Data Preprocessing

The raw data cannot be directly fed to the model so, we have performed some data preprocessing steps to make them compatible for different models.

1) *Physiological signals data*: The physiological signals were first separated from the emotions to segregate features and labels. To maintain consistency in feature scales, data normalization through standardization using the StandardScaler function from scikit-learn was employed. Subsequently, the data gets split into training, validation, and test sets, allocating 90% of the data for training and validation and reserving 10% for testing in case of LSTM and 80-20 ratio for SVM.

¹<https://github.com/bipeshrajsubedi/Multimodal-Stress-Classification-Using-Physiological-Signals-and-Facial-Expressions>

Fig. 1: Dataset distribution

Furthermore an additional step was used to create sequences for LSTM model.

2) *Facial expressions data*: After extracting pixel data and converting it into a numpy array, the code normalizes pixel values to a range between 0 and 1, a standard practice for image data. Emotion labels are encoded numerically and then one-hot encoded to facilitate categorical classification. The dataset is split into training, validation, and test sets with 10% of the data allocated for testing and the remaining 90% further divided into training (80%) and validation (20%). It is to be noted that the original dataset contains grayscale image pixels so, it must be converted to 3 channels as VGG expects 3 channels. However, the custom CNN model doesnot require this step.

C. Models Implementation for Physiological data

Fig. 2: Overall Procedures for implementing LSTM model on physiological data

1) *Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Model*: The physiological signals data after preprocessing are subjected to a function to create sequences to feed into the LSTM model as shown in Figure. 2. Each sequence contains an instance of all features and its respective output label. The LSTM model consists of a lstm layer followed by a dense layer to predict binary classes using sigmoid as an activation function. The

LSTM model consists of a total of 18241 parameters. The preprocessed data is fitted into the LSTM model for training and validation. Once it is complete the trained model is evaluated on the test set. Table. I shows the model parameters for the LSTM Model. These parameters were selected after explicit experimentation on physiological data.

TABLE I: Model Parameters for LSTM

Parameter	Value
Batch size	4
Epochs	30
Memory Units	64
Activation	Sigmoid
Loss function	Binary cross-entropy
Optimizer	Adam
Learning rate	0.001

Fig. 3: Overall Procedures for implementing SVM model on physiological data

2) *Support Vector Machine (SVM) Model*: Similarly, Figure. 3 depicts the overall procedures employed for implementing SVM on physiological data. All the procedures are similar except SVM doesn't require data to be fed in sequences, therefore it is omitted. The SVM model is trained with the model parameters shown in Table. II. It is to be noted that these parameters were selected based on the experimentation on physiological data. Similar to LSTM, the trained SVM model is evaluated on the test data to access the model's performance on the same metrics. The Radial Basis Function

TABLE II: Model Parameters for SVM

Parameter	Value
Regularization (C)	5
Kernel	rbf
gamma	auto

(rbf) was selected to handle the non-linear relationships in the data and 'auto' scaling was used as we have more samples than features in the dataset.

D. Models Implementation for Facial expression Data

The overall procedures for implementing a pre-trained CNN i.e. VGG16 and our Custom CNN is depicted in Figure 4. We opted to go for VGG16 based on the preliminary experimentation. Other pre-trained CNNs that were considered includes ResNet50, EfficientNetB0, and MobileNetV2.

Fig. 4: Overall Procedures for implementing CNN model on facial expressions data

1) *VGG16*: VGG16 is a sophisticated convolutional neural network designed for image classification. With 16 layers of learnable weights, its architecture employs repeated blocks of convolutional layers with ReLU activation and max-pooling, concluding with a fully connected layers for making classification decisions. It is Known for its effectiveness and simplicity and is widely used in the field of image recognition. As our work requires only two classes to be predicted, the top layer of the VGG16 Model was removed and a global average pooling, and dense layers were added to make predictions using softmax activation. The preprocessed data is then fitted into the model for training and validation employing the model parameters shown in Table III. The trained model is then accessed on the test set to calculate model performance. The model parameters were found to be best based on our experimentation.

TABLE III: Model Parameters for CNN

Parameter	Value
Batch size	128
Epochs	10
Activation	Softmax
Loss function	Categorical cross-entropy
Optimizer	Adam
Learning rate	0.001
Input shape	VGG16(48,48,3), Custom CNN(48,48,1)

2) *Custom CNN*: A basic CNN model is implemented with convolution, pooling, flatten, and dense layers as shown in Figure. 5. The experiments were performed on different number of layers including dropout layers but the proposed simple model performed relatively well in our study. The model parameters shown in Table. III are also applicable in

Fig. 5: Custom CNN model architecture

this case with the only difference being the input shape. It was preferred to analyze the performance of these model under the common parameters. The Custom CNN model is also trained using training and validation data after preprocessing. In this case, the pixels are not converted to 3 channels. The trained model is then evaluated on test set to find the performance metrics.

E. Model Evaluation

All the models were evaluated based on the following performance metrics: test accuracy, precision, recall, and f1-score. These metrics are widely used for classification tasks. Each class is considered equally important, regardless of its size and because of that we have opted for macro average scores.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Physiological signals data

Table. IV and Table. V shows the total number of data present in training, validation, and testing sets along with the number of data in each class used in LSTM and SVM model respectively for experimentation.

TABLE IV: Data Distribution for LSTM Model

Data	Train	Validation	Test	Classes(0,1)
15s data	28062	7016	3898	25704, 13272
30s data	59132	14783	8213	54162, 27966
60s data	120268	30068	16704	110160, 56880

TABLE V: Data Distribution for SVM Model

Data	Train	Test	Classes(0,1)
15s data	31180	7796	25704, 13272
30s data	65702	16426	54162, 27966
60s data	133632	33408	110160, 56880

1) *Model Performance:* Table. VI depicts the performance of both models on three windows of physiological data. It can be observed that LSTM have obtained better scores compared to SVM model.

TABLE VI: Model Performance on Physiological Signals Data

Data	Model	Test acc	Precision	Recall	F1
15s data	LSTM	0.80	0.79	0.80	0.79
30s data	LSTM	0.85	0.85	0.82	0.83
60s data	LSTM	0.86	0.85	0.83	0.84
15s data	SVM	0.79	0.84	0.72	0.73
30s data	SVM	0.82	0.85	0.75	0.77
60s data	SVM	0.83	0.85	0.77	0.79

Fig. 6: Training and validation accuracy and loss of LSTM model on different physiological data window

2) Findings:

- Both LSTM and SVM demonstrated promising results with LSTM having an edge over SVM on test accuracy, precision, recall and f1 score in most cases. SVM showed more competence with LSTM on 15s data having higher precision score. One of the reasons can be attributed to the ability of SVM to work better with less data as compared to deep learning models such as LSTM which required more data to learn effectively.

Fig. 7: Confusion matrices for LSTM and SVM on different physiological data windows

- It is found that 30s data and 60s data showed improved performance compared to 15s data, suggesting that capturing more extended physiological signal data enhances stress prediction accuracy.
- The confusion matrix shows that both the models performed well for class-0 predictions. However, the model's performance for class-1 predictions is not as good. One of the reasons might be the uneven distribution of data with class-0 having more instances than class-1 instances. To mitigate this problem, synthetic data generation techniques like SMOTE can be used but we opted to work with the original data to preserve the real-world characteristics. Moreover, LSTM showed better performance for class-1 prediction compared to SVM.
- The graph depicts the training and validation accuracy/loss of the LSTM model over 30 epochs. Both training and validation accuracies increase over time. Similarly, both training and validation loss lines are approaching convergence, indicating an effective learning

process. The training loss is consistently lower than the validation loss, but both are decreasing at the similar rate, suggesting a good fit without apparent overfitting.

B. Facial expressions data

Table. VII shows the total number of data present in training, validation, and testing sets along with the number of data in each class used in both the CNN models for experimentation.

TABLE VII: Data Distribution for CNN Models

Data	Train	Validation	Test	Classes(0,1)
Facial data	21974	5494	3052	13334,17186

1) *Model Performance*: Table. VIII depicts the performance of both the CNN models on facial expressions data. It can be observed that VGG16 have obtained better scores compared to Custom CNN model.

TABLE VIII: Model Performance on Facial Expressions Data

Model	Test acc	Precision	Recall	F1
VGG16	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.87
Custom CNN	0.81	0.81	0.81	0.81

Fig. 8: Training and validation accuracy and loss of VGG16 and Custom CNN model on facial expressions data

Fig. 9: Confusion matrices for VGG16 and Custom CNN on facial expressions data

2) Findings:

- Both VGG16 and Custom CNN achieved high accuracy on the training set, indicating effective learning from the training data. The high accuracy on the validation set suggests that the models generalize well to unseen data.
- VGG16 exhibits a test accuracy of 87%, indicating robust generalization to new and unseen data. Custom CNN achieves a test accuracy of 81%, demonstrating a reasonably good performance on the test set.
- VGG16 outperformed Custom CNN across various metrics, including higher training accuracy, higher validation accuracy, and a slightly better test accuracy. Despite the differences in accuracy, both models demonstrate stable precision, recall, and F1-score values with VGG16 having an edge over our Custom CNN model.
- The confusion matrix shows that both the models performed well for class-0 predictions as well as class-1 predictions, especially class-1 predictions despite having uneven distribution of data. However, the gap is not very big compared to physiological data where the data was more imbalanced.
- From the graph it can be seen that both accuracies are increasing over time, indicating that the model is learning effectively. However, there is a noticeable gap between training and validation accuracy, indicating that the model performs better on the training data than on unseen data. The training loss decreases at a faster rate compared to the validation loss, but both stabilize around after 6-7 epochs.

V. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORKS

In conclusion, this study has introduced a comprehensive strategy for stress detection, considering both physiological signals and facial expressions. The LSTM and SVM models demonstrated promising results in interpreting the complexities of physiological data, while VGG16 and a Custom CNN exhibited effectiveness in capturing facial features that signals stress. These results indicate the possibility of developing strong stress classification models, paving the way for practical implementations in real-world stress management scenarios. Even though this study shows promising results, there exist a

lot of room for improvements. Some of the future direction of this work includes:

- Exploring the potential of ensemble models to enhance overall performance by leveraging the strengths of individual models.
- Investigating the combination of physiological signals and facial expressions for a more comprehensive understanding of stress in a multimodal context.
- Collecting more data to mitigate the imbalance in the classes.
- Exploring advanced techniques for hyperparameters tuning and experimenting with other different deep learning models

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